

Influence of Year of Study on Computer Attitude of Business Education Students in Lagos, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the attitude to computer among Business Education students in Lagos State tertiary institutions. The effect of year of study of the Business Education students on their attitude to computer was studied. Four institutions of higher learning (two universities and two Colleges of Education) in Lagos State were selected for the study. The sample comprised of 520 Business Education students. The subjects responded to a computer attitudinal scale and a questionnaire comprising items on the biodata of respondents. The study adopted the ex-post-facto research approach as none of the variables was manipulated. The data collected were analysed using mean, standard deviation and ANOVA. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software was used to carry out the analysis. The result revealed the following: year of study had significant effect on the Business Education students' attitude to Computer. Useful recommendations as they affect government policies, delivery of Business Education in our tertiary institutions as well as Business Education students were made.

Keywords

Attitudes, Influence, Year of study, Computer, Business Education, Student.

1. INTRODUCTION

Computer is now a common tool in education, industry, economy, politics, culture and several other sectors. Therefore it can no longer be relegated to specialized work place settings. In education in particular, Computer is both taught and used. In spite of its importance, the level of utilization of it is still low. For instance, in Business education, the use of the typewriter is still common in typewriting classes. The low level of usage of computer implies a low attitude to it in certain quarters.

Students' attitudes to Computer represent their feelings, desires, aversions, fears, convictions and other tendencies that predispose them to act the way they do. Students' attitudes to issues or actions are not inherited, but are as a result of learning [3]. A student does not just deliberately set himself or herself to like or dislike a subject, but it is because of the sort of experience he or she had with the subject [2]. This is why attitude was viewed as an opinion, which represents a person's overall inclination towards an object, idea or institution [1]. According to [1], for a child to be properly pre-disposed to learning integrated science, he or she has to form the right

An assessment of the attitude of 200 and 300 level computer education students of Federal College of Education (special), Oyo, Nigeria towards the inclusion of computer education in Colleges of Education curriculum, showed that there was a statistical significant difference between the attitudes of the students at the different levels of study. The 200 level students showed a more positive attitude [3].

Computer attitude could be measured with the use of a scale known as 'Computer Attitude Scale (CAS). CAS is made up of four components. The first component called "Affect" is composed of six items which measure feelings towards the Computer. The second component which is the "Perceived Usefulness" (PU) is composed of five (5) items. PU measures the individual's belief about the usefulness of Computer in their jobs. The third component which is "perceived control" is composed of six items. It measures the perceived comfort level or difficulty of using Computer. The fourth component "Behavioural Intentions" measures the Behavioural Intention and actions with respect to Computer [5]

Business education practice requires the utilisation of Computer tools for both training and practice. The use of typewriter is no more popular. The computer is now required to do most of the word processing and allied duties. Besides, the accounting packages are now available for a more effective and stress free accounting. This makes the study about utilization of Computer in Business education imperative. The extent to which an individual will use it will depend on whether or not he is favourably disposed to it; hence the need for the study on the attitude of Business Education students on the utilisation of Computer. This study will test and discuss hypotheses on general (hypothesis 1) and specific (hypotheses 2-5) attitudes of Business Education students to Computer as follows:

1. No significant difference exists in the mean Computer attitudes of Business education students across their year of study.
2. There is no significant difference in the Business education students' feelings towards Computer across their year of study.
3. There is no significant difference in the Business education students' beliefs about the usefulness of Computer across their year of study.
4. There is no significant difference in the Business education students' perceived comfort level or difficulty of using Computer across their year of study.
5. There is no significant difference in the Business education students' behavioural intention and action with respect to Computer across their year of study.

2. METHOD

The study adopted an ex post facto design with the Business Education students in tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria as population for the study. Purposive sampling procedure was used. Two government owned universities (one federal government owned and one state owned) and Two government owned Colleges of Education (one federal government owned and one state owned) where Business Education courses are offered, were selected for the study. The computer attitude scale (CAS), originally developed and validated by Selwyn and later adapted by Soh was administered on 520 Business education students from the four selected tertiary institutions. CAS comprised of four components. The first component called "Affect" is composed of six items measuring feelings towards computers. The second one called "Perceived usefulness" (PU) which comprises of five items measures the individual's belief about the usefulness of computer in their studies. "Perceived Control" which is the third component is composed of six

items and measures the perceived comfort level or difficulty encountered in Computer usage. "Behavioural intentions" comprising of four items measures the Behavioural intention and actions with respect to computer usage. Each item is an attitudinal statement to which they

agreed or disagreed using the following response format: strongly agree (4), agree (3), disagree (2) strongly disagree (1). The instrument was found to have an internal validity coefficient of 0.90 and a significant construct validity ($p < 0.001$). The reliability co-efficient was found to be 0.7. It was therefore found to be reliable and so fit for the study.

3.RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results and relevant discussions are presented below in accordance with the hypotheses raised.

Hypothesis One: No significant difference exists in the mean Computer Attitudes of Business Education students across their Years of Study.

Table 1: Anova Comparison of Students' Mean Computer Attitudes Across Years Of Study.

Sourcesof Variations	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-Value
Between groups	11071.377	6	1845.229	11.261	0.000*
Within groups	84057.186	513	163.854		
Total	95128.563	519			

* Statistically significantly different at 0.05.

Table 2: Anova Comparison of students' feelings Towards Computer Across their years of study.

Sources of Variations	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-Value
Between groups	14087.562	6	2347.927	7.933	0.000*
Within groups	151.823.81	513	295.953		
Total	165911.37	519			

* Statistically significantly different at 0.05

Table 3: Anova Comparison of Students' beliefs about the usefulness of Computer across years of study.

Sourcesof Variations	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-Value
Between group	28887.837	6	4814.639	13.604	0.000*
Within groups	181557.12	513	353.913		
Total	210444.95	519			

* Statistically significantly different at 0

Table 4: Anova Comparison of Students'perceived comfort level or difficulty of using Computer across years of study.

Sourcesof Variations	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-Value
Between group	6419.200	6	1069.867	7.688	0.000*
Within groups	71389.941	513	139.162		
Total	77809.141	519			

* Statistically significantly different at 0.05.

Table 5: Anova Comparison of Students' behavioural intention and action with respect to Computer across years of study.

Sources of Variations	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-Value
Between group	5287.050	6	881.175	4.421	0.000*
Within groups	102250.42	513	199.319		
Total	107537.47	519			

* Statistically significantly different at 0.05.

Tables 1-5 presents the results of the comparison of the mean scores in the general Computer attitude as well as Affect, Perceived Usefulness, and Control and Behavioural Intention when segmented according to their years of study. The result showed that there were significant differences in the general Computer attitude of business education students across their years of study. The differences in mean scores of Affect, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Control as well as Behavioural Intention subscales were also significant.

The multiple comparisons (using scheffe posthoc analysis) of the mean scores in the general Computer attitude across their years of study showed some significant differences. Specifically the following differences in Computer attitudes across their levels of study exist.

There is a significant difference between 200 and 300 level University students' mean scores in general Computer attitudes. The 300 level University students scored higher.

There is a significant difference between 200 level University and 200 level College of Education students' mean scores in general Computer attitudes. The 200 level College of Education students scored higher.

There is a significant difference between 200 level University students and 300 level College of Education students' mean scores in general Computer attitudes. The 300 level college of Education students scored higher

There is a significant difference between 300 levels University and 100 level College of Education students' mean scores in general computer attitude. The 300 level University students scored higher.

A significant difference exists between 100 and 200 level College of Education students' mean scores in general Computer attitudes. The 200 level College of Education students had higher general Computer attitudes

A multiple comparison of the affect subscale of Computer attitudes across their years of study also showed that statistical significant differences exists across their years of study. Specifically, the following significant differences exist in the Affect subscale across their years of study:

There is a significant difference between 200 and 300 level University students' mean scores in the Affect subscale of Computer attitudes. The 300 level University students scored higher.

There is a significant difference between 200 level University and 200 level College of Education students' mean scores in the Affect subscale of Computer attitudes. The 200 level College of Education students scored higher.

There is a significant difference between 200 level University students and 300 level College of Education students' mean scores in the affect subscale of Computer attitudes. The 300 level College of Education students scored higher.

A significant difference exist between 100 level College of Education students' mean scores in the affect subscale of Computer attitudes. The 200 level College of Education students had higher score in the affect subscale.

A multiple comparison of the Perceived Usefulness subscale of Computer attitudes across their years of study also showed some significant differences statistically. Specifically, there are significant differences in the Perceived Usefulness subscale across their years of study as shown below.

There is a significant difference between 100 level University, and 200 level College of Education students' mean scores in Perceived Usefulness subscale of computer attitude. The 200 level college of Education students had higher mean scores.

There is a significant difference between 200 and 300 level University students' mean scores. The mean score of 300level is higher.

There is a significant difference between 200 level University and 200 level College of Education students' mean scores.

There is a significant difference between 200 level University and 300 level College of Education students' mean scores. The mean score of 300 level University students is higher.

There is a significant difference between 300 level University and 100 level College of Education students' mean scores. The 300 level University students had higher mean scores.

There is a significant difference between 100 and 200 level College of Education students. The 300 level students had higher mean scores.

A multiple comparison of the Perceived Control subscale of Computer attitudes across their years of study also showed some significant differences statistically. In particular, the following significant differences exist in the Perceived Control subscale across their years of study.

There is a significant difference between 200 level University and 200 level College of Education students' mean scores. The 200 level College of Education students had higher mean scores.

A significant difference exists between 100 and 200 level College of Education students. The 200 level College of Education students had higher mean scores.

A significant difference exists between 100 and 300 level College of Education students' mean scores. The 300 level College of Education students' had higher mean scores.

A multiple comparison of the Behavioral intention subscale of Computer attitudes across their years of study also showed some significant differences statistically. In particular, the following significant differences exist in the Behavioral intention subscale across their years of study.

A significant difference exists between 100 and 200 level University students. The 100 level University students had higher mean scores.

There is a significant difference between 200 levels University and 200 level College of Education students' mean scores. The 200 level University students had higher mean scores.

There is a significant difference between 200 levels University and 300 level College of Education students' mean scores. The 300 level College of Education students had higher mean scores.

There is a significant difference between 200 and 300 level University students. The 300 level University students had higher mean scores.

In this study, the year of study had significant impact on respondents' attitudes to Computer. The finding in this study confirms the finding of [3] but contradict the finding of [4]. The disparity in the findings could be explained by the geographical scope of the study. [3] and the current study drew sample from a single state whereas [4] drew his sample from Lagos and Ogun States.

4. CONCLUSION

The purpose of the study was to investigate Business Education students' Attitude to Computer. It also studied the influence of years of study on Business Education Students' attitude to computer. It could therefore be concluded that years of study is a strong factor in determining Business Education students' attitude to Computer.

5. RECOMMENDATION FOR IMPLEMENTATION

Based on the findings of this study and the conclusion drawn, the following are suggested for implementations.

The government should intensify her effort on the Computer based policies. The policies should be reviewed to lay more emphasis (especially at the University level) on practical skill acquisition.

In the delivery of Business Education courses, students should be encouraged and compelled to use Computer tools.

The activities of students' professional associations should be geared towards encouraging the use of Computer.

By now, the computer should be made to completely replace the typewriter. In other words, typewriter should be phased out completely.

Each Business Education student should be encouraged to have his/her own personal computer.

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